

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No5(5)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 704 sahifa,
22-may, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
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va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
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reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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FORMING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The rapid transformation of modern education requires schools not only to provide academic knowledge but also to foster students' social and emotional development. Emotional intelligence has become one of the key competencies that determine an individual's ability to understand, manage, and express emotions effectively while maintaining positive interpersonal relationships. This article examines the role of extracurricular activities in the formation of emotional intelligence among primary school students. The study analyzes the pedagogical potential of extracurricular programs, including clubs, creative groups, sports activities, and social projects, in developing emotional awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivation, and social skills. Furthermore, the article discusses the theoretical foundations of emotional intelligence and proposes practical approaches for integrating emotional learning into extracurricular environments.

Key words: emotional intelligence, primary education, extracurricular activities, emotional development, empathy, self-regulation, social skills, social-emotional learning, personality development, educational psychology.

Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy ta'limning jadal rivojlanishi maktablardan nafaqat akademik bilim berishni, balki o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy va emotsional rivojlanishini ham ta'minlashni talab etmoqda. Emotsional intellekt shaxsning his-tuyg'ularni anglash, boshqarish va samarali ifodalash, shuningdek, ijobiy shaxslararo munosabatlarni yo'lga qo'yish qobiliyatini belgilovchi muhim kompetensiyalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida emotsional intellektni shakllantirishda sinfdan tashqari faoliyatlarning o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda to'garaklar, ijodiy guruhlar, sport mashg'ulotlari va ijtimoiy loyihalar kabi sinfdan tashqari dasturlarning emotsional xabardorlik, o'zini boshqarish, empatiya, motivatsiya va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishdagi pedagogik salohiyati yoritilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada emotsional intellektning nazariy asoslari muhokama qilinib, emotsional ta'limni sinfdan tashqari muhitga integratsiya qilishning amaliy yondashuvlari taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: emotsional intellekt, boshlang'ich ta'lim, sinfdan tashqari faoliyatlar, emotsional rivojlanish, empatiya, o'zini boshqarish, ijtimoiy ko'nikmalar, ijtimoiy-emotsional ta'lim, shaxs rivojlanishi, ta'lim psixologiyasi.

Аннотация: Стремительное развитие современного образования требует от школ не только предоставления академических знаний, но и содействия социальному и эмоциональному развитию учащихся. Эмоциональный интеллект является одной из ключевых компетенций, определяющих способность человека понимать, контролировать и эффективно выражать свои эмоции, а также поддерживать позитивные межличностные отношения. В данной статье рассматривается роль внеурочной деятельности в формировании эмоционального интеллекта у учащихся начальных классов. В исследовании анализируется педагогический потенциал внеурочных программ, включая кружки, творческие объединения, спортивные занятия и социальные проекты, в развитии эмоциональной осознанности, саморегуляции, эмпатии, мотивации и социальных навыков. Кроме того, в статье обсуждаются теоретические основы эмоционального интеллекта и предлагаются практические подходы к интеграции эмоционального обучения во внеурочную среду.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональный интеллект, начальное образование, внеурочная деятельность, эмоциональное развитие, эмпатия, саморегуляция, социальные навыки, социально-эмоциональное обучение, развитие личности, педагогическая психология.

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary educational system is increasingly focused on the holistic development of learners. Alongside cognitive and academic achievements, educators are expected to cultivate students' emotional, social, and moral competencies. In recent decades, emotional intelligence has gained considerable attention among researchers and practitioners due to its significant influence on academic success, social adaptation, and psychological well-being.

Primary school age represents a crucial period in children's emotional and social development. During this stage, children learn to recognize and regulate emotions, interact with peers, establish friendships, and respond appropriately to various social situations. The effectiveness of this developmental process largely depends on the educational environment and opportunities provided by schools.

Extracurricular activities offer a unique context for emotional learning because they create informal, interactive, and engaging environments where students can express themselves freely. Unlike traditional classroom instruction, extracurricular programs emphasize collaboration, communication, creativity, and practical experiences. Consequently, they serve as powerful tools for nurturing emotional intelligence and promoting students' personal growth.

In the twenty-first century, emotional intelligence has become a critical factor in personal and professional success. Numerous studies indicate that individuals with high emotional intelligence are more capable of coping with stress, building healthy relationships, and achieving long-term goals. Therefore, educational institutions are increasingly recognizing the importance of developing emotional competencies from an early age.

Despite significant progress in educational technologies and instructional methodologies, many schools continue to prioritize academic achievement over emotional development. As a result, students may experience difficulties in managing emotions, resolving conflicts, and maintaining positive social interactions. Such challenges can negatively affect both learning outcomes and psychological health.

Extracurricular activities provide valuable opportunities for addressing these issues. Through participation in clubs, artistic programs, sports teams, and community service projects, students acquire practical emotional and social experiences that cannot always be achieved within formal classroom settings. Therefore, investigating the role of extracurricular activities in fostering emotional intelligence among primary school students remains a highly relevant and significant research topic.

The aim of this study is to investigate the role of extracurricular activities in developing emotional intelligence among primary school students and to identify effective pedagogical approaches for enhancing emotional competencies.

The objectives of the study are:

1. To analyze the theoretical foundations of emotional intelligence.
2. To examine the educational value of extracurricular activities.
3. To identify the components of emotional intelligence that can be developed through extracurricular participation.
4. To determine pedagogical conditions that facilitate emotional development.
5. To provide practical recommendations for educators and school administrators.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of emotional intelligence was first introduced by Peter Salovey and John Mayer in the early 1990s. They defined emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive, understand, manage, and utilize emotions effectively. Later, Daniel Goleman popularized the concept and emphasized its importance in educational and professional contexts.

Despite the constant improvement of forms and methods of work, there are significant gaps in the development of cognitive abilities in oral speech. Previously, the student was completely subordinate to the teacher, now active actions, thoughts, ideas and doubts are expected from him. Most classes contain children of different levels of readiness, which requires tasks of different levels of difficulty. The teacher must develop any student according to individual abilities and identify the creative capabilities of each individual. Each lesson lasts 35 minutes. During classes, the student develops developed forms of self-awareness, self-control and self-esteem. The absence of grades reduces anxiety and unreasonable worry among students, and the fear of wrong answers disappears. As a result, children develop an attitude towards these activities as a means of developing their personality. The classes use entertaining and easy-to-understand tasks and exercises, tasks, questions, riddles, games, puzzles, crosswords, which is attractive for younger schoolchildren to develop oral speech. Most of the time in class is occupied by children independently solving search problems. Thanks to this, children develop the ability to act independently, make decisions, speak correctly, and manage themselves in difficult situations. Through new approaches, methods, and technologies, promote the speech development of children. A child's oral speech skills are formed under the influence of many factors. That is why it is so important to create conditions for children's speech activity, for communication, for expressing their thoughts.

Researchers such as Howard Gardner, Lev Vygotsky, Jean Piaget, and Erik Erikson have also contributed to understanding children's emotional and social development. Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences highlights interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence as essential components of human competence. Vygotsky emphasized the role of social interaction in cognitive and emotional growth, while Piaget and Erikson examined developmental stages that influence emotional maturation.

Recent studies in social-emotional learning (SEL) demonstrate that emotional competencies can be effectively developed through structured educational experiences. International organizations, including UNESCO and OECD, advocate integrating social-emotional learning into educational systems to prepare students for the challenges of modern society.

Although numerous studies have explored emotional intelligence in educational settings, further research is needed to identify effective extracurricular strategies specifically designed for primary school students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research approach based on the analysis of scientific literature and pedagogical sources related to emotional intelligence and extracurricular activities. The research involved theoretical analysis, comparison, and synthesis of educational and psychological studies. Particular attention was given to the role of extracurricular programs, including clubs, sports activities, creative groups, and social projects, in fostering emotional intelligence among primary school students. The collected information was analyzed using descriptive and comparative methods to identify effective pedagogical approaches for emotional development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Emotional intelligence refers to an individual's ability to recognize, understand, regulate, and appropriately express emotions while effectively interacting with others. According to contemporary psychological theories, emotional intelligence consists of several interconnected components:

1. Self-awareness;
2. Self-regulation;
3. Motivation;
4. Empathy;
5. Social skills.

Self-awareness enables children to identify and understand their emotional states. Self-regulation allows them to manage emotional reactions and maintain behavioral control. Motivation encourages persistence and goal-oriented behavior. Empathy promotes understanding of others' feelings, while social skills facilitate effective communication and cooperation.

These competencies are particularly important during primary school years because they form the foundation for future academic, social, and professional success.

Extracurricular activities represent organized educational experiences conducted outside formal classroom instruction. These activities include academic clubs, arts programs, sports competitions, environmental projects, cultural events, and volunteer initiatives.

Such activities create authentic situations where students interact with peers, solve problems collaboratively, and experience diverse emotions. As a result, they provide ideal conditions for emotional learning and personal development.

Participation in extracurricular programs encourages students to take responsibility, express opinions, respect diversity, and develop leadership qualities. Moreover, the informal nature of these activities reduces anxiety and creates a supportive environment for emotional growth.

Empathy is one of the most important dimensions of emotional intelligence. It involves understanding and sharing the feelings of others. Group-based extracurricular activities promote empathy by encouraging students to cooperate, communicate, and support one another.

Drama clubs, storytelling sessions, collaborative projects, and community service activities allow children to experience different perspectives and understand the emotions of their peers. These experiences contribute significantly to the development of emotional sensitivity and social responsibility.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

When organizing extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren in various conditions of the educational process, the principle of illustration and clarity in teaching remains leading in teaching, since the peculiarity of primary schoolchildren is: visual-figurative thinking, reading poems. Taking this feature into account, we create visual aids, tables, diagrams, drawings, from which the child can draw, expressively read, read information syllable by syllable: read correctly, analyze, summarize, voice, characterize. It should be noted that all manuals are simple and understandable. In addition, emotional and intellectual illustration also involves the use of such techniques as dramatization of literary works, fairy tales, proverbs, which contributes to the development of the spiritual and moral sphere through the development of ethical feelings, goodwill and emotional and moral responsiveness, understanding and empathy for the feelings of other people. And the most important thing is to master the skills of semantic reading of Russian texts of various styles and genres. That is why we consider "Children's Theater" to be one of the important areas of extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech. We have been teaching this course in schools for several years now. With performances and productions, our students annually perform oral readings in front of elementary school students and parents. We share our best practices with colleagues and help them in their work. She introduced teachers to the peculiarities of her work and at seminars, speaking at round tables, and conducted open lessons in schools in the city of Termez, the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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2026. №5(5)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.